

DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF ULTRASONOGRAPHY IN ACUTE APPENDICITIS TAKING HISTOPATHOLOGY OF REMOVED APPENDIX AS GOLD STANDARD

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Abstract

Objective: We aim to assess the diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound in acute appendicitis diagnosis using histopathology of removed appendix as a gold standard.

Study design: Prospective cohort study

Place and Duration of Study: In a Tertiary care hospital, Rawalpindi, from May 2024 to January 2025.

Methodology: 120 patients were included for US based on their Alvarado scores (4-7). Following US imaging patients were scheduled for laparoscopy. Variables comprised of gender, age, Alvarado score, ultrasound findings including; appendix size, free fluid, lack of compressibility, thickness of walls, increased vascularity, and presence of appendicolith. US diagnosis was standardized against histopathological findings as extent of inflammatory infiltrate, mucosal and submucosal changes (ulcerations, edema, necrosis, or fibrinous exudate). Histopathological results of removed appendix were compared with US findings by crosstabulation.

Results: Out of 120, there were 75 (62.5%) male and 45 (37.5%) female patients having Alvarado score in between 4-7. Acute appendicitis was confirmed in 85 patients by histopathological examination. 84 out of 85 patients were accurately diagnosed through ultrasound (US) by keeping histopathology as a gold standard. Sensitivity and specificity of this procedure were 98.82% and 91.43% having diagnostic accuracy of 96.67% respectively. 35 patients out of 120 had other pathological conditions confirmed by histopathological examination, in which non-specific abdominal pain was the most common and present in 11 patients.

Conclusions: Study concluded that ultrasound might be used as non-invasive approach to histopathological diagnosis, which is invasive technique used for acute appendicitis diagnosis. Ultrasound is safe, effective and non-invasive technique in diagnosis.

INTRODUCTION

Acute appendicitis is the most common type of abdominal surgical emergency⁽¹⁾. Clinical diagnosis becomes difficult in certain cases which present without classical information of migratory pain toward umbilicus, lower right quadrant (LQR) of abdomen. Gynecological and other pathologies related to bowel can cause difficulties in diagnosis⁽²⁾. Studies show that the risk of acute appendicitis perforation increases by 5% every 12 hours and surgery should not be delayed beyond 36 hours after diagnosis⁽³⁾⁽⁴⁾. Diagnosis based only on patient history and clinical examination can increase negative appendectomy rate. This leads to postoperative complications, increasing mortality rate. However, using diagnostic imaging techniques can decrease this number bringing it as low as 6-10%⁽⁵⁾.

White cell and anti-granulocyte scintigraphic scans are time-consuming, expensive, and not sensitive in diagnosis of acute appendicitis⁽⁶⁾. Computed tomography scan (CT scan) is sensitive and specific for diagnosis of acute appendicitis but chance of missed pathology is higher due to narrow field of vision⁽⁴⁾. CT scan also proven to be an expensive procedure and uses ionizing radiation which makes it less favorable for frequent imaging.

American College of Radiology labeled ultrasound (US) as “may be appropriate” for suspected patients of acute appendicitis, presenting with pain in lower quadrant of abdomen⁽⁷⁾. With introduction of Pulyaert technique of graded compression sonography, in 1986, diagnostic criteria significantly improved over years⁽⁷⁾. US proves to be a better diagnostic tool in terms of its sensitivity and specificity in diagnosing pathologies of lower abdomen⁽⁸⁾. Having obvious advantages over other methods such as non-invasive, non-ionizing radiation, easy availability, and no specific pre-procedure requirements for patients

Due to its feasibility US has become first choice procedure in diagnostic routines. In differential diagnosis of patients with Alvarado score <4, acute appendicitis is ruled out. Patients with Alvarado score >7 almost certainly have acute

appendicitis⁽⁹⁾. But for those having an Alvarado score between 4-7, patient history and clinical examination are not enough and using US decreases unnecessary laparotomies. Examination of removed appendix by histopathologist provides an accurate diagnosis and confirmation of acute appendicitis⁽¹⁰⁾. Histopathological examination of appendix is considered gold standard because examination at tissue level rules out any other pathology (Crohn’s disease) that might mimic signs of acute appendicitis.

Objective of this study was to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound (US) in detection of acute appendicitis by keeping histopathology as gold standard. Study aimed to determine the efficacy of US imaging in identification of acute appendicitis cases, contributing to improved diagnostic reliability and clinical-decision making in emergency settings.

Methodology

The prospective cohort study was conducted at Tertiary care hospital, Rawalpindi, Pakistan, after taking ethical approval (ERC Letter no: Ser No. 798), from May 2024 to January 2025. Patients admitted to ED, due to acute and severe pain in right lower quadrant of abdomen suspected to have acute appendicitis, were candidates for ultrasonographic diagnosis and histopathological examination of removed appendix as gold standard. Sample size of 120 was estimated using 95% confidence interval with sensitivity and specificity of US as 97.84% and 90.90% with 10% margin of error and 7%⁽¹¹⁾ prevalence of acute appendicitis.

Patients presenting with sudden onset of severe lower abdominal pain, Alvarado score between 4-7 and patient underwent US examination were included. Patients with contraindications for US (such as extensive obesity, bowel gas obscuring appendix, or skin conditions preventing adequate scanning), prior appendectomy, pregnant women or patients unwilling to take part in study were excluded.

Firstly, procedure was explained to patient who met research criteria, informed consent was

taken. Patients were asked to lay in supine position for US procedure. US was conducted using GE Logic G-6 machine, by using curvilinear probe with a frequency between 3.5-5 MHz applying Puylaert technique (graded compression). An appendix appearing normal or not visualized on US was considered as negative result. Consequently, diagnostic test results were classified as either positive for appendicitis (when the appendix was visualized and showed any suggestive findings of acute appendicitis) or negative for appendicitis (no appendicitis).

On imaging, patients having enlarged appendix (greater than 6-7mm), thickened walls, and peri-appendiceal fluid or abscesses were scheduled for appendectomy. Laparoscopic appendectomy was performed and specimens were sent for histopathological examination. Microscopic changes were recorded. Features including neutrophilic infiltration and edematous or fibrous changes in muscularis propria or serosa was assessed.

Outcome measures were clearly defined as follows: patient demographic parameters (gender, age), Alvarado score, ultrasound findings included; appendix size, free fluid, lack of compressibility, thickness of walls, increased vascularity, and presence of appendicolith. Diagnosis of US was standardized against histopathological findings as extent of inflammatory infiltrate, mucosal and submucosal changes (ulcerations, edema, necrosis, or fibrinous exudate). Data were collected from US images reviewed by researchers who were blind to histopathological findings. Initially reviewed data were compared with US reports for each acute appendicitis case. Accuracy of US findings were re-examined and analyzed in confirmed patient of acute appendicitis. To find and relate most frequent observations in images.

Patients were observed for 24 hours after treatment to evaluate if there were any complications or negative effects, i.e., infection, bleeding, or bowel obstruction. Follow-up examinations involved assessment of patient-

reported outcomes and clinical examination to promptly address any negative effects.

R-Studio 2024.04.0+735 was used for data analysis. For categorical variables, percentages and frequencies were calculated. Crosstabulation was made to assess the diagnostic accuracy of acute appendicitis among test (ultrasound) and gold standard (histopathology) diagnostic method.

Results:

A total of 120 patients, out of which seventy-five were males (62.5%) and forty-five were females (37.5%). Most of patients had age range from 21 to 40 years, comprising 62.5% of sample population. Male proportion dominated the female proportion. BMI, age, and Alvarado scores of the positive and negative patients are described in Table I. All patients with Alvarado score between 4-7 participating in this study were examined for acute appendicitis by US. Appendix was examined by histopathologist for confirmation of pathological condition. In US findings, positive diagnosis tenderness at McBurney's point and increased vascularity were the most prominent findings present in 100% of observed patients. Increased size of appendix and lack of compressibility were also considerably important factors present in 91.76% and 95.29% of patients respectively. Most prominent histological findings include loss of submucosal integrity and edema of mucosal lining. Signs of inflammation observed in US and histological findings are described in Table II. Out of 120 cases labeled as acute appendicitis, 85 were confirmed by histopathological examination. In remaining 35 cases, non-specific abdominal pain was most common (11 patients). Frequency and modality of other pathologies confirmed by histopathology are described in Table III.

Sensitivity and specificity of this procedure were 98.82% (95% CI, 93.63 - 99.94%) and 91.43% (95% CI, 77.62 - 97.04%) with diagnostic accuracy of 96.67% (95% CI, 91.74 - 98.70%) respectively, confirmed by histopathology as in Table IV.

Table I. Patient Characteristics and Alvarado Score Findings Categorized by Histopathological Results (N=120)

Variable	Total Patients; n (%)	Positive Patients; n (%)	Negative Patients; n (%)
Gender			
Female	45 (37.5%)	32 (71.11%)	13 (28.89%)
Male	75 (62.5%)	53 (70.67%)	22 (29.33%)
Age			
01 - 20	27 (22.5%)	20 (74.07%)	7 (25.93%)
21 - 40	75 (62.5%)	51 (68%)	24 (32%)
41 - 60	10 (8.33%)	8 (80%)	2 (20%)
61 - 80	7 (5.83%)	6 (85.71%)	1 (14.29%)
81 - 100	1 (0.83%)	0 (0%)	1 (100%)
BMI Score			
18.5 - 24.9	27 (22.5%)	19 (70.37%)	8 (29.63%)
25.0 - 29.9	38 (31.67%)	23 (60.53%)	15 (39.47%)
≥ 30	55 (45.83%)	43 (78.18%)	12 (21.82%)
Alvarado Score			
Four	43 (35.83%)	22 (51.16%)	21 (48.84%)
Five	34 (28.33%)	25 (73.53%)	9 (26.47%)
Six	19 (15.83%)	15 (78.95%)	4 (21.05%)
Seven	24 (20%)	23 (95.83%)	1 (4.17%)

Table II. Ultrasound and Histopathological Findings in Acute Appendicitis, Taking Histopathology as Gold Standard (N=85)

Variable	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Ultrasound		
Observed Diameter of Appendix	78	91.76
Sonographic Mcburney's Tenderness	85	100.00
Presence of Free fluid in the Surrounding	58	68.24
Lack of Compressibility	81	95.29
Increased Vascularity	85	100.00
Presence of Appendicolith	18	21.18
Histopathology		
Loss of Submucosal Integrity	85	100.00
Signs of Ulceration	19	22.35

Edema of Mucosal Linning	85	100.00
Necrosis	12	14.12
Presence of Fibrinous Exudate	10	11.76

Table III. Final Diagnosis Excluding Acute Appendicitis (N = 35)

Final Diagnosis	No. of Patients
Nonspecific Abdominal Pain	11
Gastroenteritis	6
Gynecologic Disease	4
Renal/Ureteric Stone	3
Tuberculous Lymphadenopathy	3
Cecal Diverticulitis	2
Infected Renal Dialysis	2
Typhlitis	2
Right Pleural Effusion	1
Urinary Tract Infection	1

Table IV. Outcomes of Ultrasound Findings in Acute Appendicitis Diagnosis Taking Histopathology as a Gold Standard (N=120)

Total Cases; n	120	
Cases Proven on Histopathology; n	85	
Ultrasound	Histopathology	
	Positive (n)	Negative (n)
Positive (n)	84	3
Negative (n)	1	32
Sensitivity	98.82% (95% CI, 93.63 - 99.94 ¹)	
Specificity	91.43% (95% CI, 77.62 - 97.04 ¹)	
PPV	96.55% (95% CI, 90.35 - 98.82 ¹)	
NPV	96.97% (95% CI, 84.68 - 99.84 ¹)	
DA	96.67% (95% CI, 91.74 - 98.70 ¹)	

¹(Wilson Score)

Discussion:

Acute abdominal pain is one of the most common modalities in presenting complaints of patients in emergency department (ED). Acute appendicitis having prevalence of 7% in these patients⁽¹¹⁾. As it mimics many common symptoms of different pathologies of abdomen,

differential diagnosis is difficult to process. Patients history and physical examination are not sufficient for diagnosis⁽¹²⁾. Different imaging techniques are under-debate for their specificity and accuracy as a diagnostic modality that includes CT scan and US⁽¹³⁾.

Repeated imaging improves visualization and minimized the incidence of false positive results. For this purpose, we choose a non-ionizing, cost effective imaging modality for examination. In this study we analyzed the role of US in accurate diagnosis of acute appendicitis. A definitive positive or negative US result in our study produced clinically significant likelihood of acute appendicitis diagnosis. Use of graded compression technique for acute appendicitis using US has reported variable sensitivity in diagnosis ranging from 44-100%⁽¹²⁾.

120 patients met the inclusion criteria of Alvarado score were examined by US and scheduled for laparoscopy. Histological findings of removed appendix were compared with US findings of same patients. Histopathology confirmed acute appendicitis in 85/120 patients. Out of these 84 patients were positively diagnosed using US. One case was proven to be negative on histological examination and labeled as false positive which could be due to misinterpretation. Sensitivity of this procedure was 98.82%. Male and female population was not balanced in term of numbers in sample population of study. This result compliments the observation made in previous study stating that male population was relatively more susceptible for acute appendicitis.⁽¹⁴⁾ According to previously available data, the accuracy in diagnosing acute appendicitis by US is greater in male population, diagnosis in female patient is usually influenced by gynecological factors that precipitates increased ratio of complications⁽¹⁵⁾. On the contrary results of positive diagnosis between two genders have comparable accuracy, and female population has overall better diagnostic accuracy in our study. Positive diagnosis made by US in females and male patients was 71.11% and 70.67% respectively. The visualization of intra-abdominal structures in obese patients is challenging due to presence of subcutaneous fat and US gives variable accuracy.⁽¹⁶⁾ In our study the number of patients with BMI >30 were greater in number which influenced the final ratio of accuracy. Nonetheless US is relatively the quicker and easily available diagnostic tool for obese patients as well. Patient's age does not

have any significant effect on accuracy of US diagnosis. This observation is similar to findings present in study by Lounis Y⁽¹⁷⁾.

.High value of PPV 96.55% encourages it to be used as a first line diagnostic tool for acute appendicitis. Observed sensitivity and specificity of US in our study is 98.82% and 91.43% supplementing the results of systemic review done by Cho Su.⁽¹⁸⁾ The details of other confirmed pathologies is discussed in Table III which suggests that Alvarado score is non-specific for acute appendicitis diagnosis and has a greater incidence of false positive which increases the need of developing a reliable imaging protocol with US.

The study did not take account of the patient's fasting status, bowel movement history and retrocecal location of appendix which could cause variable results. Patient population did not have a highly variable ethnicity which might create a bias if results are implied internationally. Selection bias may be suspected if diagnosis of acute appendicitis was made in excluded patients, as participants were selected on the basis of clinical presentation of acute appendicitis. Recently developed laparoscopic techniques of diagnosis and CT scan comparison were not added due to their high cost. The relation of accurate diagnosis by US and years of experience of clinicians was not recorded in this study. In an article by Alelyani M⁽⁴⁾, it is reported that ultrasound interpretation by clinicians does not show any significant correlation between the years of experience and accurate diagnosis of acute appendicitis by US.

US shows great accuracy as a diagnostic tool for a number of procedures. Its role in acute appendicitis has more potential to be explored by improving probe technique and patient guidelines in future studies.

Conclusion:

Acute appendicitis is the most common acute abdominal condition that requires immediate diagnosis and surgery. Our study demonstrates high value of sensitivity and specificity in accurate diagnosis of acute appendicitis by ultrasound. Ultrasound is safe, effective and non-invasive

technique and might be used as first-line diagnostic tool for acute appendicitis in emergency department. Combining clinical symptoms with ultrasound findings will significantly increase the accuracy of acute appendicitis diagnosis.

Conflict of Interest: There is no any conflict of interest.

Author's Contribution: Contribution of Authors in manuscript:

AZ & JA: Designing study, analysis of data, collecting of data, data analysis and final manuscript review.

ND & UN: Data interpretation, collecting data, critical reviews, manuscript writing and final review.

MK & US: Interpretation of data, collection of data, and final review.

Authors agreed to investigate and resolve any questions regarding authenticity or integrity of their work in great detail and to take full responsibility.

REFERENCES

1. Teng TZJ, Thong XR, Lau KY, Balasubramaniam S, Shelat VG. Acute appendicitis—advances and controversies. *World J Gastrointest Surg.* 2021 Nov 27;13(11):1293–314. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4240/wjgs.v13.i11.1293>
2. The Importance of Ultrasound Findings in Children with Acute Abdominal Pain to Prevent Unnecessary Surgery. *Syst Rev Pharm [Internet].* 2020 Jun 1 [cited 2024 Sep 15];11(04). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31838/srp.2020.4.56>
3. Quevedo-Fernandez E, Gonzalez-Urquijo M, Hinojosa-Gonzalez DE, Morales-Flores LF, Morales-Morales CA, Zambrano-Lara M, et al. Analysis of deferral times in patients diagnosed with acute appendicitis. *Asian J Surg.* 2023 Mar;46(3):1187–92. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asjsur.2022.08.053>
4. Alelyani M, Hadadi I, Shubayr N, Alashban Y, Alqahtani M, Adam M, et al. Evaluation of Ultrasound Accuracy in Acute Appendicitis Diagnosis. *Appl Sci.* 2021 Mar 17;11(6):2682. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11062682>
5. Depetris MA, Martínez Chamorro E, Ibáñez Sanz L, Albillos Merino JC, Rodríguez Cuellar E, Borrueal Nacenta S. The usefulness and positive predictive value of ultrasonography and computed tomography in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis in adults: A retrospective study. *Radiol Engl Ed.* 2022 Nov;64(6):506–15. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rxeng.2020.10.009>
6. Tolia DrD. Role of ultrasound in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis: A prospective study. *Int J Radiol Diagn Imaging.* 2020 Jan 1;3(1):05–8. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33545/26644436.2020.v3.i1a.50>
7. Chulroek T. Accuracy of ultrasonography in diagnosis of acute appendicitis at King Chulalongkorn Memorial Hospital. *Chulalongkorn Med J [Internet].* 2024 Mar 7 [cited 2024 Sep 15];67(1). DOI: [10.14456/clmj.2023.9](https://doi.org/10.14456/clmj.2023.9)
8. Academic Emergency Medicine - 2017 - Matthew Fields - Accuracy of Point-of-care Ultrasonography for Diagnosing Acute.pdf. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/acem.13212>

9. Al-Tarakji M, Zarour A, Singh R, Ghali MS. The Role of Alvarado Score in Predicting Acute Appendicitis and Its Severity in Correlation to Histopathology: A Retrospective Study in a Qatar Population. *Cureus*. 2022 Jul 15 [cited 2024 Sep 15]. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.26902>
10. Rahman S, Karim SN, Al Tanzim SMM, Kabir E, Sen S, Bristy FR, et al. Histopathological Study of Appendectomy Specimens in a Rural Tertiary Care Hospital in Bangladesh. *Mediscope*. 2023 Apr 11;10(1):17-21. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3329/mediscope.v10i1.65406>
11. Omari AH, Khammash MR, Qasaimeh GR, Shammari AK, Yaseen MKB, Hammori SK. Acute appendicitis in the elderly: risk factors for perforation. *World J Emerg Surg*. 2014 Dec;9(1):6. DOI: [10.1186/1749-7922-9-6](https://doi.org/10.1186/1749-7922-9-6)
12. Fu J, Zhou X, Chen L, Lu S. Abdominal Ultrasound and Its Diagnostic Accuracy in Diagnosing Acute Appendicitis: A Meta-Analysis. *Front Surg*. 2021 Jun 28;8:707160. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsurg.2021.707160>
13. Chen KC, Arad A, Chen KC, Storrar J, Christy AG. The clinical value of pathology tests and imaging study in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis. *Postgrad Med J*. 2016 Oct 1;92(1092):611-9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/postgradmedj-2015-133865>
14. Wainsani S, Khoiriyah K. Penurunan Intensitas Skala Nyeri Pasien Appendiks Post Appendektomi Menggunakan Teknik Relaksasi Benson. *Ners Muda*. 2020 Jul 20;1(1):68. DOI: <https://ejournal.seaninstitute.or.id/index.php/health/article/download/1030/834>
15. Capoglu R, Gonullu E, Bayhan Z, Coskun M, Harmantepe T, Kucuk F. Comparison of scoring systems regarding the gender as a parameter with the traditional scoring systems for predicting appendicitis. *Updat Surg*. 2022 Jun;74(3):1035-42. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13304-022-01272-y>
16. Lehmann B, Koeflerli U, Sauter TC, Exadaktylos A, Hautz WE. Diagnostic accuracy of a pragmatic, ultrasound-based approach to adult patients with suspected acute appendicitis in the ED. *Emerg Med J*. 2022 Dec;39(12):931-6. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/emered-2019-208643>
17. Lounis Y, Hugo J, Demarche M, Seghaye MC. Influence of age on clinical presentation, diagnosis delay and outcome in pre-school children with acute appendicitis. *BMC Pediatr*. 2020 Dec;20(1):151. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12887-020-02053-5>
18. Cho SU, Oh SK. Accuracy of ultrasound for the diagnosis of acute appendicitis in the emergency department: A systematic review. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2023 Mar 31;102(13):e33397. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000033397>